

Olive Seed Tannins as Bioadhesives for Manufacturing Wood-based Panels

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Abstract— The olive seed is a by-product of the olive oil production industry. Biuret test and ferric chloride test revealed that water or alkali NaOH extractions of olive seed flour is rich in proteins and tannins. Both protein and tannins are well known bio-based wood adhesives in the wood-based panel industry. In general, tannins-based adhesives show better mechanical and physical properties than protein wood adhesives. This paper explores different methods of extracting tannins from olive seed flour against the tannins yield and their applications as bio-based adhesives in wood-based panels. Once investigated, the physical and the mechanical properties of wood-based panels made using bio-adhesives based tannins extracted from olive seed flour revealed that the resulting products seemed to satisfy the Japanese Industrial Standards JIS A 5908:2015.

Keywords— Bio-adhesives, Olive seed flour, Tannins, Wood-based panels.

I. INTRODUCTION

Olive mill waste *alperujo* contributes to significant environmental issues in Mediterranean areas where 97% of total olive production in the world takes place [1]. The olives industry produces more than 30 million cubic metres of *alperujo* which is highly toxic due to the high concentration of aromatic compounds [2]. The toxicity of the effluent coming from the olive oil industry is attributed to the high content of phenolic constituents (from 1.5 gl^{-1} to 8 gl^{-1}). [3]. *Alperujo* is a powerful source of phenolic compounds compared with olive oil [4]. Natural highly polymerised phenolic compounds such as tannins are available in olive mill wastes [5]. The olive seed can be removed from olive stone by crushing. Olive stone flour is used as fillers to give smooth-flowing powder mixture [6]. A cross-section of an olive is shown in Fig. 1. Tyrosol and hydroxytyrosol can be found in olive stones, and verbascoside and nuzhenide can be found in olive seeds. Both seeds and stones contain oleuropein [7, 8]. Some mills remove the stone from the olive pulp. Currently, the stone is used as an energy source as it contains high calorific power [9] and activated carbon [10]. Olive stones contain a high amount of ligno-cellulosic materials such as lignin. The phenolic compounds contained in the olive stones can be extracted [7]. In addition, sugars were identified by enzymatic hydrolysis in the olive stone's fibrous part [11]. High-added value compounds such as

proteins, fats, phenols, free sugars, phenolics, hemicellulose, cellulose and lignin are contained in the olive stone [11]. Furfural, which is used as a lignin-crosslinking agent [12] in wood glue, can be produced by using acid hydrolysis of olive stones [13]. Olive stone flour has been used as a cheaper reinforcing filler in a polypropylene matrix [14].

Fig 1: Cross section of olive fruit [15]

It has been reported that a phenol-formaldehyde wood adhesive can be developed by using olive stones [16]. The olive kernel could replace 15% of base resin in a phenol-formaldehyde wood adhesive exhibiting better adhesive properties compared to the commercial phenol-formaldehyde wood adhesives [1]. Thermogravimetric analysis has indicated that there is no thermal degradation of the olive stones up to 195°C . It has also been shown that the resistance to fungi of wood particleboard made by adding olive stone powder was increased [17]. Tannin is a well-known bio-based adhesive used in the wood panel industry. It has been found that liquid effluent of *alperujo* consists of tannins in addition to polyphenols, polyalcohols, pectins, and lipids [18]. It is a renewable resource obtained as a by-product of the agriculture industry [19]. In another study,

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HCl has been used to extract tannins as the soluble components from olive seed [20].

The adhesion properties of olive stone fibre reinforced polystyrene can be enhanced by treating the fibres with 4% of NaOH solution before production of the composite. The alkaline treatment remarkably improved the tensile strength and reduced hydrophilic nature of olive seed fibre [21].

Tannin, so-called tannic acid, is a well-known bio-based wood adhesive which can be used even in exterior grade applications due to its high water-resistance property [22, 23, 24, 25, 26]. Tannins from different types of biomasses can be extracted by using different extraction methods such as extraction with organic solvents, hot water, ionic liquids, supercritical fluids, pressurised hot water or subcritical water, by microwave and by ultrasound [27]. Seed extractions showed component of tannin (gallic and ellagic acid derivatives) available in it [28, 29].

In this study, tannin was extracted from olive seed flour by using a refluxing method. It was then used as a bio-based wood adhesive to make particleboards by using virgin wood particle and recycled wood particles, and their mechanical and physical properties were investigated.

II. METHODOLOGY

Firstly, the availability of tannins in olive seed flour was qualitatively tested and this was then followed by a quantitative test. Extracted tannins were then mixed with wood particles to make particleboard samples. They were then subjected to mechanical and physical tests and the values compared to industrial standards.

A. Materials

Olive seed flour from netuxa.com and FeCl₃, Whatman No 1 Filter papers, Kaolin, Gelatine solution, Indigo Carmine were purchased from Fisher Scientific UK Ltd. Kastamonu Entegre in Adana Turkey provided 1 mm virgin wood particles. Recycled wood particles of size 1 mm were provided by French Inst. of Tech. for Forest-based and Furniture Sector.

B. Methods

In order to extract tannins from olive seed flour, the flour was added either to distilled water or to distilled water and 1M NaOH in a ratio of 1:25 (w/w). The tannins extraction was then performed by using a reflux method with a magnetic stirrer at 90°C for 2 hours. The decoction was then cooled and filtered through a Whatman No.1 filter paper. The filtrate was then tested with 2-3 drops of 5% (w/v) aqueous solution of ferric chloride for the formation of greenish precipitate indicating the presence of tannins in the sample. The quantitative analysis of tannin was performed by the Official Methods of Association of Analytical Chemists [30]. First, 5 ml of aliquot of the extract was mixed with 12.5 ml of indigo-carmine solution with 375 ml of distilled water. Then the mixture was titrated against standardised 0.1N KMnO₄ solution (3.16 g of KMnO₄ in 1 l of purified water) of 'Y' ml until the blue colour of the indigo-carmine becomes final yellow at the end point as in Figures 10.3a and 10.3b. The 'Y' amount of KMnO₄ was used to

calculate the concentration of total tannins and the concentration of other related compounds (non-tannins) in the same extract were estimated as explained below.

To determine the concentration of non-tannins in the extract, another 50 ml of an aliquot of the extract was mixed with 25 ml of gelatin solution, 50 ml of acidic NaCl solution (25 ml of concentrated H₂SO₄ added to 975 ml of saturated NaCl solution) and 5 g of powdered kaolin. The mixture was then shaken for 15 min and filtered through Watman No. 1 filter paper. Then 12.5 ml of the filtrate was mixed with 12.5 ml of the indigo-carmine solution and 375 ml of distilled water. The mixture was then titrated KMnO₄ solution of 'X' ml until the final yellow endpoint.

(a) Refluxing of olive seed flour.

(b) Qualitative test for the existence of tannin of the extract. The green precipitate when ferric chloride is added to the extract is in right

Fig. 2 Extraction and qualitative test of olive seed flour.

The volume of KMnO₄ used to titrate the exact amount of tannin in 1 ml of the extract can be taken from the difference of Y/5 and X/12.5 [31]. The equations 10.1 and 10.2 were used to estimate the tannin concentration of olive seed flour extract.

$$1 \text{ ml of standard KMnO}_4 \text{ solution} = 0.595 \text{ ml of 0.1N Oxalic acid} \quad (10.1)$$

$$1 \text{ ml of 0.1N Oxalic acid} = 0.0042 \text{ g of tannin} \quad (10.2)$$

It is needed to have 200 g of oven-dried wood particles and 70 g of dry adhesive powder to make a laboratory-scale particleboard in this study. In order to achieve a yield of 70 g of tannins, 933 g of olive seed flour was used for the extraction with NaOH. The filtrate of the extraction was then heated until its mass was reduced to 220 g, consisting in 70 g of tannin and 150 g of water, which was necessary to increase the moisture content of the final wood particle and adhesive mixture up to 20%. Afterwards, the thick extract was mixed with the oven-dried virgin wood particles to make the first particleboard sample. The mixture was then hot pressed to make a particleboard sample. The cured particleboard was cut to size for physical and mechanical tests overall values compared against JIS A 5908:2015. Then the same procedure was done for recycled wood particles.

(a) Indigo-carmin and the extract mixture.

(b) End point of the titration against KMnO_4 .

Fig. 3 Qualitative analysis for available tannin

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tannin extraction from olive seed flour was done using distilled water with and without 1M NaOH and the resulting yield was compared. The yield of the extraction of tannin performed using NaOH was better than that carried out with distilled water extraction as shown in Table 1.

The mechanical and physical properties are reported in the Table 2. In general, usage of recycled wood particles exhibited better results for mechanical and physical properties of the particleboard satisfying industrial standards. This is due to the

already present synthetic adhesive content in the recycled wood particles. The density of particleboard samples made by using recycled wood particles is higher in value than the samples made of virgin wood particles. This is due to the less porous nature of recycled wood particles. Less porous nature also reduced the moisture content and thickness swelling of recycled wood particles. Increase in the elastic modulus of recycled wood particleboards indicates a more brittle material than virgin wood made particleboards. Previously used synthetic adhesive content in recycled wood particles is also the causes for the increase in internal bond strength.

TABLE 1
COMPARISON CALCULATION OF TANNIN YIELDS FROM
DISTILLED WATER AND 1M NaOH EXTRACTION METHODS.

Solvent	Distilled water	NaOH
Y (ml)	12.5	18.5
X (ml)	7.5	9.0
KMnO_4 used for tannin + other compounds in 1 ml of the extract (ml)	2.5	3.7
KMnO_4 used for other compounds in 1 ml of the extract (ml)	0.6	0.72
KMnO_4 used for tannin in 1 ml of the extract (ml)	1.9	2.98
Tannin in 1 ml of the extract (g)	0.00475	0.007447
Tannin in 1 g of olive seed flour (g)	0.04748	0.07447
The percentage of tannin available in olive seed flour (%)	4.8	7.5

TABLE 2
MECHANICAL AND PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF PARTICLEBOARD
SAMPLES MADE BY USING 65% OF VIRGIN WOOD PARTICLES AND
35% OF TANNINS AND OTHER COMPOUNDS EXTRACTED FROM
OLIVE SEED FLOUR BY USING 1M NaOH EXTRACTION.

Property	Virgin wood particles	JIS Type 8 Satisfied?	Recycled Wood particles	JIS Type 8 Satisfied?
Bending strength (N m^{-2})	7.8	✗	10.9	✓
Elastic modulus (N m^{-2})	1854	✗	2152	✓
Density (kg m^{-3})	698	✓	802	✓
Internal bond strength (N m^{-2})	0.17	✓	0.22	✓
Moisture content (%)	15	✗	11	✓
Thickness swelling (%)	15	✓	12	✓

IV. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

Tannins are a well-known bio-based wood adhesive used at industrial level. In most cases, it is blended with some other synthetic adhesives to enhance its properties. Tannins can be blended with formaldehyde-based adhesives as well as non-formaldehyde-based adhesives such as pMDI. The results in this study have shown that tannins extracted from olive seed flour can be used without blending with synthetic adhesives to make particleboards with recycled wood particles which satisfied the industrial standards. However, it seems necessary to blend tannins with synthetic additives or adhesives to

manufacture boards with virgin wood particles to achieve industrial standards.

The olive seed tannin resin content used in this study was 35%. Increase in the resin content could enhance the mechanical and physical properties of the samples to achieve JIS standards for virgin wood particles.

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